

A MODERN APPROACH TO TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10008198>

Abstract: The article deals with the modern technological method Dogme in teaching English as a foreign language within a communicative methodology. This method implies a complete or partial rejection of textbooks and technology in favor of real communication.

Key words: communication, communicative approach, dogme method, textbook-free learning, lack of learning materials, spontaneous language.

Nowadays foreign language becomes not only a means of communication in a multicultural space, but also a tool for personality formation and identifies the level and quality of education of general cultural competences of students[4]. The learning process implies a complex process which is conditioned by the subjective-personal interest of the learner. Motivation, intention, aim, aspiration, as well as need are characterized by the degree of relevance of a given activity [5]. With this in mind, we need completely new methods and technologies in foreign language teaching.

In recent years, the concept of "shifting the focus from teaching" has become dominant in higher education. That is, the classical fundamental approach (learning grammar and memorizing dialogues) has been replaced by the communicative method [2]. Within the framework of this method, foreign methodologists distinguish the Dogme method. The novelty of this method lies in the transition from the usual cognitive aspect to the psychological one, as well as in the rejection of teaching methods and technologies.

For the first time the Dogme method came to light in 2000 in an article by Methodist Scott Thornburg where he criticized the use of supplementary material in the teaching process, saying that it only overburdens and complicates the process [6]. The name and principle for the new approach came from the avant-garde film movement Dogma 95. This methodology is based on several points outlined in the "Dogma 95 Manifesto:

- Creating "the right conditions" to communicate;
- Organizing conversations ("managing conversation"), i.e. spontaneous exchanges on topics that concern everyone. The teacher plays the role of a participant but not that of an organizer;

- Selecting stimulus to share" which is the teacher's proactive role.
- focusing on form" or investigating language directly in conversation
 - "learning from lesson to lesson" and reinforcing it with various techniques and exercises[3].

As Scott Thornburg and Luke Madison put it in Teaching Unplugged: Dogme in English Language Teaching. The modern lesson should not be overloaded with textbooks and manuals, and proposes a move away from the usual methodology where "going beyond" is not possible, suppressing the learner's initiative [7]. As an alternative, scholars highlight live conversation based on real-life experience, using the grammar and vocabulary that the students are familiar with at this stage of learning. They also highlight three "precepts" of the Dogme method

- Learning-communication;
- Minimum use of textbooks;
- "Living" language.

It should be noted that "communication-based learning" is similar to the modern communicative approach. This methodology involves the learner in the process of communicating here and now with the "people in the room", gently guiding them to form and formulate their own words correctly. The lesson is seen as a social event. Luc Medings also talks about this, referring to the term 'zone of proximal development' coined by L.S. Vygotsky. According to this model, what the learner does together with the teacher today, he or she will be able to do on his or her own tomorrow.

Despite the opinion of Dogme opponents who argue that the main disadvantage is the lack of a plan and the transfer of initiative to students who do not have sufficient knowledge of the language. Besides, without knowing the structure of the language it is impossible to fully acquire communicative competence. Proponents claim that saturation with textbooks only distracts the learners and point out that another advantage of the Dogme method is the total freedom from external factors which allows a reduction in the distance between the teacher and the learners, thus making it possible to better the learners. The teacher is not dependent on Internet access, manuals or photocopies, the lesson can take place anywhere [1].

"Spontaneity" of language is based on addressing current language needs. For example, repeating the same phrases ("dribbling"), helps to remember words and grammatical structures and to correct speech errors by recording and recycling the produced speech errors.

In this method, language is a means of creating and maintaining social relationships.

In contrast to the communicative approach which emphasizes the use of the language learnt both in tasks and in reality, the Dogme method emphasizes live communication between teacher and learner. That's why many current teachers call for a combined communicative approach in order to make practice and communication more productive[8].

In general, the Dogme method is based on communication, without being linked to textbooks. It's more than a method, it's a new level of teaching which emphasizes the development of the potential of learners through communication, the use of personal experience and the situational presentation of the language.

To conclude, it is fair to say that the application of this modern method or some of the principles individually within the communicative method in higher education can contribute to the most productive interaction between students and teacher, reinforcing. It is fair to say that the use of this modern method, or several of the principles of the communicative method, in the context of higher education, can help students and teachers interact with each other in the most productive way possible, strengthen their self-confidence, overcome language barriers, reach a modern level of foreign language proficiency, and ensure a comfortable and unforced speech, as this method makes it possible to solve many everyday and professional situations and to leave them with dignity.

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